

THE TASK OF MORAL EDUCATION OF CHILDREN OF PRESCHOOL AGE
AND MEANS OF IMPLEMENTATION.

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Abstract: The task and content of the moral education of children of preschool age requires the education and development of the child's spiritual world, his mind, moral feelings, and personal qualities. Education of moral feelings, ideas and behavior in children. Providing moral knowledge fulfills a number of educational tasks, a broad vision and understanding of the moral values of human life and culture is provided.

Key words: morals, manners, educational value, personality, development, environment, humanitarianism, love of country.

Preschool age is a period when the child actively explores the world around him. Preschool children have their own characteristics of psychological development. When he starts walking, the child makes a lot of discoveries, gets acquainted with things in the room, on the street, in the kindergarten. Collecting different things, studying them, listening to the sounds coming from the subject, he knows what qualities and characteristics this object has. Scientists have proven that at this young age, the child remembers this information, after which he will never remember it in life. This is the period when the child is interested in anything that can expand his horizons, and this supports the world around him.

The formation of moral consciousness, emotions and behavior, which are important spiritual qualities of a person, patriotism, love for the country, respect for the coat of arms, flag, anthem of Uzbekistan, humanitarianism, attitude to work, attitude to joint research, conscious discipline and other the development of feelings is the basis of moral education. The task and content of moral education of children of preschool age requires education and development of the child's spiritual world, his mind, moral feelings, and personal qualities. Providing moral education fulfills a number of educational tasks, provides a wide range of ideas about the moral values of human life and culture. Ethical ideas affect the formation of concepts such as vision, reasoning, evaluation and, on this basis, increase moral belief, i.e.: It helps children to observe and enrich their own moral experiences; It creates the ground for moral education of the person. Ethical knowledge is mainly carried out through ethical conversations, lectures, evenings, meetings with various professionals and other means. Moral education in preschool educational institutions is carried out using various means. First of all, it is carried out by introducing children to the work of adults through various activities, by providing education during and outside of training. All kinds of holidays, social life events, children's literature, music, game materials, media! - the world, radio, etc. have a great influence on the moral education of children.

Young children acquire moral imagination and knowledge well only in games. Their conscious understanding of the moral concepts acquired by children is carried out first in training, then in games, work processes, outings, and independent activities. It is important to use various methods and methods in providing moral education to children of preschool age. Moral education methods are a method of activity aimed at acquiring moral imagination and knowledge of children.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-3, ISSUE-3

Through all the methods mentioned above, children are taught moral norms and rules, events of social life. Moral ideas and concepts are formed in them. The main requirements for the methods of this group are: Taking into account children's ideas about good and bad; active participation of children in a specially created situation for discussing the norms of moral behavior; to treat each child's feelings with care. It is strictly forbidden to criticize the child inappropriately, laugh at him, ignore him. All methods are used consistently and comprehensively.

In the hadiths of the Prophet PBUH about people living together in society, supporting each other, and the preference of the few over the many; "Two people are better than one, three people are better than two people, four people are better than three people, be with many people. "God unites the ummahs only to follow the right path," it is said. When good days and bad days befall people, the neighborhood and relatives will definitely help. We can see this in our prayers. For example: hashars, coming to the wedding with hooves, etc.

The doctrine of community, which is an important factor of personality formation, occupies an important place in moral education. For this, it is necessary to gradually organize the children in several small groups, and then involve them in doing something together. The goal should be clear to children. It should be organized in such a way that every child participates in the general work, even if only a little. Art, children's holidays, joint work and activities play a big role in the education of such characteristics. It is of particular importance that children's games and work are part of a team. These teach children to act together, to direct their aspirations towards a common goal, to manage their own work and purpose by subordinating the work and movement of management. From a young age, a child feels the need to communicate with others, with a group of children, and to be together. But a small child cannot choose a team by himself. He will come to any team as required by the circumstances. He starts attending pre-school educational institutions in his place of residence or his parents' place of work. The child does not go to these institutions voluntarily. Nevertheless, the child must obey the rules and regulations of this community, follow its procedures. Otherwise, the team will not forgive him. As a result, the child is forced to learn the morals and manners that he lives. That is why the great thinker A. Navoi recommends that the child participate in the community of intelligent and virtuous people and enjoy their conversations from a young age.

Cultivating a sense of humanity. Humanity occupies an important place among the moral characteristics and rules of conduct for preschool children. A sense of humanity develops on the basis of teaching moral norms and rules. For this, it is necessary to teach children to do good deeds. It is necessary to take into account the age of children in the education of humanity. Telling a small child to be good does not make him good, because he lacks the life experience to correctly analyze good and bad. Children of this age are taught to do good deeds; Helping a fallen child up, tucking in his clothes, comforting, caring for plants and animals, giving a toy to a friend, showing a place to a standing person, most importantly to teach others to be happy with the service rendered.

Cultivating the qualities of humility, correctness, honesty and cheerfulness. These characteristics are considered to be the most important factors in raising a healthy person. Humility is one of the most important and noble qualities of every human being. It is mainly brought up from school age. But starting from preschool age, it is necessary to teach children a sense of humility, to lose pride, arrogance and boasting. Preschool children try to put themselves ahead of other children, sometimes they brag about their parents' profession. In this case, it is necessary to work with the parents of the children, to explain the necessity and importance of each profession

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-3, ISSUE-3

with specific examples. If the children succeed in some tasks and humiliate other children, the educator explains to the child that he should teach something to his friend who does not know something, that it is not appropriate to praise oneself. Cultivating honesty and truthfulness is inextricably linked with the prevention and fight against lying and dishonesty. Some children try to make the fairy tales they have heard from adults look like they saw in their dreams. Even in this case, it is necessary to praise "Ertak" for being able to weave well without fighting. Thus, positive results can be achieved if positive examples of children's character are brought up with all effective methods of moral education, taking into account their age characteristics. Education of patriotism. Patriotism as a social, historical and moral feeling appears during the social development of a person. In the primitive community system, patriotism was a feeling related only to one's relatives, mother's blood, and traditions, but with the emergence of classes, the ideas of patriotism deepened and spread to more and more areas of social life. went deeper. Over time, this feeling has become a great power.

Love of country is one of the deepest social feelings. In our country, the feeling of love for the Motherland is combined with the feeling of internationalism. The feeling of love for the motherland in preschool children is brought up by adults with a certain consistency, taking into account the mental development of children and the clarity and imagery of their thinking. Therefore, the feeling of love for the motherland in children of this age is brought up through clear facts and bright examples that are close and familiar to them. International education. Our republic is international in its essence. That is why it is important to educate children of preschool age about internationalism and friendship between peoples. Education of preschool children in the spirit of internationalism is based on the goal of creating a positive attitude towards other nationalities and peoples, a feeling of interest in the life of different peoples. The development of such feelings is perfected mainly through imitation. Meetings with representatives of each nation living in brotherly republics to form the basis of international feelings for preschool children; reading literature about their traditions, culture, art, and nature in special trainings, holding conversations, showing pictures, showing slides, and telling stories about the lives of the children of the nation it will be useful to read.

In short, children of preschool age morally the task of upbringing and means of implementation are important spiritual qualities of a person formation of moral consciousness, feelings and behavior, patriotism, to the motherland love, respect for the coat of arms, flag, anthem of Uzbekistan, humanitarianism, attitude to work, attitude to joint research, Conscious discipline and development of other emotions is important in moral education .The task is to educate preschool children morally the task and content of the child's spiritual world, the moral feelings of his mind requires training and development of personal qualities and behavior.

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